

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF SMALL SCALE WATER TURBINE BY USING RPRT FOR ENERGY HARVESTING

MRS. URMILA S. ZOPE

Engineering sciences and allied engineering department, Professor (Mechanical) at Bharti Vidyapeeth's college of Engg for Women, (BVCOEW), Pune-43, India, Email- ums3333zope@gmail.com

MRS. DIKSHA P. CHOPADE

Engineering sciences and allied engineering department, Professor (Electrical) at Bharti Vidyapeeth's college of Engg for Women, (BVCOEW), Pune-43, India, Email- dikshachopade@gmail.com

MRS. PRATIBHA M. KARANDIKAR

Mechanical engineering department, PREC Loni, Tal Rahata, Dist- Ahmednagar, Ahmendnagar, India, Email- pkarandikar04@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Natural resources like river, stream, waterfall can be used for the generation of power. In this the horizontal axis impulse turbine is designed in which water jet is impulsed which strikes tangentially on the integrated vanes or rotor. Turbine designing is for small application, where limited power is generated which can be utilised for lighting a power bulb or for battery charging. Working on this topic resulted into design & manufacture of the small scale low cost & low weight turbine, for which rapid prototype manufacturing technique is used and suggested. Turbine manufactured by RP technique is not suitable for commercial use but for small application in remote areas where reach of electrification grid is impossible.

KEYWORDS: RP, Energy harvesting, design & manufacture, turbine design.

I.INTRODUCTION:

Small scale water turbine which is also known as microhydro power turbine. micro hydro turbines are developed from last centuries back. Means the use of natural water source for the power generation is a old technique exist. In this work, new design of turbine alongwith low and low cost, low weight manufacturing techniques introduced. Also anlysis of the turbine vane is done.

II.DESIGN FOR THE TURBINE PROTOTYPE:

Very initial consideration for the microhydro turbine is limited space availability ranging from 1 to 5 feet for installing that designed turbine. Accordingly limitations are kept to the sizes of the turbine parts.

A. 2D DIAGRAMS OF A DESIGNED PARTS:

Turbine assembly drawing

Rotor1 (Diameter 135)

Rotor2 (diameter 175)

Rotor3 (Diameter 235)

shaft

Insert

Stand2

Ring

III.PARTS GEOMETRIES WITH DIMENSIONS:

- 1) Vanes (integrated) circular subtended angle is kept 120° with height 32mm & depth 10 to 12mm.
- 2) Rotor-135mm, 175mm and 225mm diameter.
- 3) $D_p =$
Pitch diameter(considering integrated vanes)of the rotor
150,200 and 250mm
- 4) No of blades-08.
- 5) Insert, which is fitted into rotor, through which shaft is passing, dimension is

$\varnothing 45 \times \text{length } 45.$

- 6) Bearings –two types
 - a. Ball bearing-NO 1205-Inner Diameter 25, outer diameter-52, width 12mm.
 - b. Cylindrical roller bearing no-16005, Inner diameter 25, outer diameter 47, width 08mm.
- 7) Flow velocity $V_f = 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5 \text{ and } 3 \text{ m/sec}$
- 8) N rotational speed of the rotor= limit 150 to 430rpm.
- 9) Net head $H_n = 1 \text{ feet to } 5 \text{ feet.}$
- 10) Gravitational acceleration $g=9.81\text{m/sec}^2$
- 11) $Q = \text{flowrate of waterstream} =$
 $\text{minimum } 0.0176 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{sec}^3}, \text{ maximum } 0.1472 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{sec}^3}.$
- 12) $R_L = \text{Length of the rotor} = 45\text{mm}$
- 13) $B_C = \text{chord of the blade}$
- 14) $\omega = \text{rotational speed of the rotor} = \frac{2\pi N}{60}$
- 15) $\text{RPM of Rotor} = 38.6 \times \sqrt{H_n/D_r}$
- 16) $V_F = \text{Impact velocity of water.}$
- 17) $\theta = \text{angle of blade} = \text{subtended} - 120^\circ$

IV.DESIGN STEPS:

(from design of high efficiency cross flow turbine for hydropower plant by Bilal Nasir)

- A) The design procedure of the **cross-flow turbine** involves the **following steps**:

1. Preparing the site data

This involves the calculations and measuring the net head of the hydro-power plant and its water flow rate.

- a. **Calculation of the net head (Hn):**

$$H_n = H_g - H_f \quad (\text{m}) \quad (1)$$

Where,

H_g = the gross head which was the vertical distance between water surface level and the intake at the turbine. This distance can be measured by modern electronic level levels.

H_f = total head losses due to the open channel, trash rack, intake, penstock and gate valve. These losses were approximately equal to 10% of gross head.

- b. **Calculation of the water flow rate (Q):**

The water flow rate can be calculated by measuring river or stream flow velocity (V_r) and river cross-sectional area (A_r), then:

$$Q = V_r \times A_r \quad (\text{m}^3/\text{sec}) \quad (2)$$

2. **Calculation of turbine power (Pt)**

The electrical power of the turbine in Watt can be calculated as:

$$P_t = Q \times H_n \times \rho \times g \times \eta_h \quad (W) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- Q discharge [m³/s]
- H_n gross head [m]
- η_h hydraulic efficiency [-]
- ρ water density [kg/m³]
- g gravitational acceleration [m/s²]

FOR FURTHER CALCULATION:

Following are the known values

$$\rho = 1000\text{kg/m}^3$$

$$g = 9.81\text{m/s}^2$$

Consider, $\eta_h = 0.85\%$

3. Calculation of turbine efficiency (Pt)

The maximum turbine efficiency can be calculated as:

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{1}{2} \times C^2 \times (\cos^2 \alpha + \psi) \times \cos^2 \alpha \quad (4)$$

where ψ = blade roughness coefficient (0.98)

From above equation it is clear that for maximum turbine efficiency, the angle (α) should be kept as small as possible.

4. Calculation of the turbine speed (N):

The correlation between specific speed (N_s) and net head H_n is

for the cross-flow turbine as following,

$$N_s = \frac{513.25}{H_n^{0.505}} \quad (5)$$

Also the specific speed in terms of turbine power in Kw, turbine speed in (r.p.m) and net head in (m) is given as , [9]

$$N_s = N \times \frac{\sqrt{Pt}}{H_n^{1.25}} \quad (6)$$

From above equations (5) and (6) , the turbine speed can be calculated as:

$$N = 513.25 \times H_n^{0.745} / \sqrt{Pt} (\text{rpm}) \quad (7)$$

5. Calculation of runner outer diameter (D_o)

At maximum efficiency, the tangential velocity of the runner

Outer periphery is given as [26]

$$V_{t_r} = \frac{1}{2} \times C \times (\sqrt{2} \times g \times H_n) (\cos \alpha) \quad (8)$$

Also as we know,

$$V_{tr} = W \times \frac{D_o}{2} = 2\pi ND_o/120$$

(9)

By comparing eq. (8) & (9) the runner outer diameter can be calculated as :

$$D_o = 40 \times \frac{\sqrt{H_n}}{N} \quad (m)$$

(10)

6. Calculation of blade spacing (S_b):

The thickness of jet entrance t_{je} measured at right angles to the tangential velocity of runner is given as [26]

$$t_{je} = k \times D_o \quad (m)$$

(11)

Where $K = \text{constant} = 0.087$

The tangential blade spacing (S_b) is given as [26]

$$S_b = \frac{t_{je}}{\sin \beta_1} = k \times \frac{D_o}{\sin \beta_1}$$

(12)

Where, β_1 - blade inlet angle = 30° , when Attack angle $\alpha = 16^\circ$

$$\text{Thus, } S_b = 0.174 \times D_o$$

(13)

7. Calculation of the radial rim width (α):

It is the difference between the outer radius (r_o) and inner radius (r_i) of the turbine runner, and it must be equal to the blade spacing and can be given as:

$$\alpha = 0.174 \times D_o$$

(14)

8. Calculation of the runner blade number (n):

The number of the runner blade can be determined as :

$$n = \pi \times D_o / S_b$$

(15)

9. Calculation of the water jet thickness (t_j):

It is also defined as nozzle thickness and can be calculated as

$$t_j = \frac{A_j}{L}$$

Where, $A_j = \text{Jet area}$

$$\text{As, } Q = A_j \times V_j$$

$$\text{Therefore, } t_j = \frac{Q}{L \times V_j}$$

$$Q / [C \times (\sqrt{2 \times g \times H_n}) \times L] = 0.233 \times Q / (L \times \sqrt{H_n})$$

(16)

10. Calculation of runner length (L):

The runner length in (m) can be calculated as:

From reference [26]

$$L \times D_o = 0.81 \times Q / \sqrt{H_n} \quad (\text{it is in metric units})$$

(17)

$$L \times D_o = 210 \times Q / \sqrt{H_n} \quad (\text{it is in british units})$$

(18)

As we know, $D_o = 40 \times \sqrt{H_n} / N$

Putting above value in equation ----- (17)

$$L = Q \times N / (50 \times H_n)$$

(19)

By putting above value of 'L' into equation of Jet thickness (t_j),

$$t_j = \frac{A_j}{L}$$

We obtain,

$$t_j = 11.7 \times \frac{\sqrt{H_n}}{N} \quad (20)$$

From eq. of D_o ,-----

$$\frac{\sqrt{H_n}}{N} = \frac{D_o}{40}, \text{ so putting in equation----- (20)}$$

$$t_j = 11.7 \times \frac{D_o}{40}$$

$$t_j = 0.29 \times D_o \quad (m) \quad (21)$$

11. Calculation of the distance between water jet and center of runner shaft (y_1)

$$y_1 = 0.05 \times D_o \quad (\text{Imperial relation})$$

(22)

12. Calculation of the distance between water jet and the inner periphery of runner (y_2) [26]

$$y_2 = 0.05 \times D_o$$

(23)

13. Calculation of inner diameter of the runner (D_i)

$$D_i = D_o - 2 \alpha$$

(24)

14. Calculation of the radius blade curvature (r_c) [26]

$$r_c = 0.163 \times D_o \quad (25)$$

15. Calculation of the blade inlet and exit angles (β_1 and β_2) [26]

The blade inlet angle can be calculated as,

$$\tan \beta_1 = 2 \times \tan \alpha$$

The blade exit angle $\beta_2 = 90^\circ$ for perfect radial flow, but it must be equal to β_1 at maximum efficiency.

(26)

V. APPROACH FOR DESIGNING:

Idea of designing integrated vanes/blade on rotor having some thickness, & shape is somewhat semicircular whose subtended angle is kept 120° , is came from the concept of banki water turbine. The difference between banki water turbine design & the turbine designed in this paper is that, bucket which having specific dimensions are mounted on the rotor by nuts and bolts while turbine discussed here having integrated vanes on the rotor this design may reduce the

overall cost of the design & manufacture. The tangential water flow falling on the vanes causes the vanes to rotate & ultimately rotates the rotor, & to the keyed shaft. The shaft on which rotor is mounted is supported in stand by means of ball bearing in the stand.

For deciding geometry profile of the vane the reference is taken from paper 'Design & manufacture of micro zero head turbine for power generation which was published in 2011'.

A thought behind designing semicircular vane is that when water strikes tangentially & go downwards to enter into next vane, maximum mass of water should enter cause the rotation of rotor to fulfill the purpose. The thickness of vane is decided from strength to thickness ratio.

By referring number of papers, the relationship of applied force of water can be given as-

$$F_i = \rho \times A \times V \times (V - u)$$

Where, F_i = Impact force (initial force)

ρ = water density.

V = Free stream/waterfall velocity.

A =Designed vane area.

u =tangential velocity of vane.

It is to be decided to kept 8 numbers of vanes on the rotor whose outer diameter is 135mm, & space angle between two blades is maintained is 45°, when falling some particular height is tangential to the back surface of the vane, means initially the velocity of the blade is assumed to be zero, it means

So, ' F_i '= initial force of water can be calculated as-

$$F_i = \rho \times A \times V \times (V - 0) \quad \text{Initially } u=0$$

$$F_i = \rho \times AV^2$$

As water enters into semicircular vane, entered mass of water not sufficient to rotate vane so again its initial velocity u is considered as zero. But angle between two consecutive vanes kept 45°, denoted as α . One important thing is that flow of water on the blade is kept tangential to rotate the rotor in one direction only. So angle between waterflow & the back surface of a vane is considered as α which is kept 0 to 5°.

$$\text{Chord area} = \frac{\theta}{360} \times \text{Arc length}^2$$

$$\text{Chord area} = \frac{120}{360} \times 32^2$$

$$\text{Area} = 10.667 \text{mm}^2$$

$$\text{i.e. Area} = 0.0010667 \text{m}^2$$

From above equation: $F_i = \rho \times AV^2$

Take value of $V_f = 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3 \text{m/sec}$

$$1). F_i = 1000 \times 0.0010667 \times (1)^2$$

$$F_i = 1.0667 \text{N}$$

$$2). F_i = 1000 \times 0.0010667 \times (1.5)^2$$

$$F_i = 2.4 \text{N}$$

$$3). F_i = 1000 \times 0.0010667 \times (2)^2$$

$$F_i = 4.2668 \text{N}$$

$$3). F_i = 1000 \times 0.0010667 \times (2.5)^2$$

$$F_i = 6.6668 \text{N}$$

$$4). F_i = 1000 \times 0.0010667 \times (3)^2$$

$$F_i = 9.6 \text{N}$$

From above explained designed procedure,

As circumference of rotor is $2\pi R = 2 \times \pi \times 75 = 471.23 \text{mm}$

And blade spacing is $S_b = 0.174 \times D_o$

$$S_b = 0.174 \times 150$$

$$S_b = 26.1$$

So, no of blades will be $\frac{471.23}{26.1} = 18.05 \approx 18 \text{ nos.}$

But we are taking minimum numbers of blades i.e. 08.

VI. CALCULATIONS:

Approach to design this turbine starts from space availability accordingly maximum size is decided for the turbine. In this some parameters are assumed-

ρ_w =water density 1000kg/m³

g =gravitational acceleration 9.81m/s²

H_n =Net head assumed 0.5 & 1m.

η_h =hydraulic efficiency assumed 80% \approx 0.8

D_r =Rotor diameter=135mm

D_p = Rotor pitch diameter=150mm

V_f =Flow velocity=1m/s; 1.5m/s; and 2m/s.

As we know, $P = \rho_w \times g \times H_n \times \eta_h \times Q$

But, $Q = \text{Area of turbine} \times \text{Flow velocity}(V_f)$

For flow velocity $V_f=1 \text{m/s}$.

$$Q_1 = \frac{\pi}{4} (Dp^2) \times V_f$$

$$Q_1 = \frac{\pi}{4} (0.15^2) \times 1$$

$$Q_1 = 0.0176 \text{m}^3/\text{s}$$

II-For flow velocity $V_f=1.5 \text{m/s}$

$$Q_2 = \frac{\pi}{4} (Dp^2) \times V_f$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{\pi}{4} (Dp^2) \times 1.5$$

$$Q_2 = 0.0265 \text{m}^3/\text{s}$$

III-For flow velocity $V_f= 2 \text{m/s}$

$$Q_3 = \frac{\pi}{4} (Dp^2) \times V_f$$

$$Q_3 = \frac{\pi}{4} (Dp^2) \times 2$$

$$Q_3 = 0.0353 \text{m}^3/\text{s}$$

Case I- For Net head **1 feet means 0.3m.**

$$P_1 = \rho_w \times g \times H_n \times \eta_h \times Q_1$$

$$P_1 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.3 \times 0.8 \times 0.0176$$

$$P_1 = 41.43 \text{ watt}$$

$$P_2 = \rho_w \times g \times H_n \times \eta_h \times Q_2$$

$$P_2 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.3 \times 0.8 \times 0.0265$$

$$P_2 = 62.39 \text{ watt}$$

$$Q_3 = Q_p \times Q \times Q_p \times Q_h \times Q_3$$

$$Q_3 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.3 \times 0.8 \times 0.0353$$

$$P_3 = 83.11 \text{ watt}$$

Case II- For Net head **0.5m.**

$$Q_1 = Q_p \times Q \times Q_p \times Q_h \times Q_1$$

$$P_1 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.5 \times 0.8 \times 0.0176$$

$$P_1 = 69.06 \text{ watt}$$

$$Q_2 = Q_p \times Q \times Q_p \times Q_h \times Q_2$$

$$Q_2 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.5 \times 0.8 \times 0.0265$$

$$P_2 = 103.986 \text{ watt}$$

$$Q_3 = Q_p \times Q \times Q_p \times Q_h \times Q_3$$

$$Q_3 = 1000 \times 9.81 \times 0.5 \times 0.8 \times 0.0353$$

$$P_3 = 138.51 \text{ watt}$$

VII.MATERIAL AND MANUFACTURING:

Selection of material: for the designed parts, as FDM RP technology is finalized to manufacture those parts so ABSM30-thermoplastic material is decided, to use this material having following properties: ABS M30 (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene M30) is 25 to 70 percent stronger than standard ABS (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene).

Greater tensile, impact, and flexural strength than standard Stratasys ABS.

Layer bonding is significantly stronger for a more durable part than standard Stratasys ABS.

Versatile Material: Good for forming functional applications.

ABS M30 parts are stronger, smoother and have better feature details.

Tensile strength=36Mpa.

Tensile elongation=10%

Flexural stress=61Mpa

Izod impact=139J/m

Heat deflection=96°

Unique properties= Variety of color options.

Density of material=(at 20°C or 68°F) >1 g/cm³(>8.345lb/in³)

Young's modulus= Modulus of elasticity= 1.4 -3.1(10⁹ N/m² OR GPA)

VIII.FORTUS SYSTEM OF FDM RP TECHNIQUE:

Fortus 3D production system offer unparalleled versatility and capability to turn CAD files into real parts, which are tough enough to be used as advanced conceptual models, functional prototyping, manufacturing tools and end use-parts. Variety of products can be produce just by loading different files and materials, which is not possible by traditional machining processes. Fortus system can produce a real end use thermoplastic parts directly form CAD files

without using expensive tooling. Fortus 3D system is streamline process from design through manufacturing, reducing costs and eliminating traditional barriers along the way.

IX.SOFTWARE USED IN FDM:

Insight software: Insight software prepares 3D digital parts files (o/p as and .STL file) to be manufactured on a fortus system by automatically slicing and generating support structure and material extrusion path in a single push of button. If necessary user can override insights defaults to manually edit parameters that control the look, strength and dimension of parts as well as the time throughput, expenses and efficiency of the FDM process.

Control center software: is a software that communicates between the user workstations and fortus system, managing jobs and monitoring the production status of fortus system. It provides control to maximize efficiency, throughput and utilization while minimizing response time. This software is included with Insight software.

X. Flowchart for manufacturing of pico hydro turbine

XI.THEORY OF DESIGN:

Under this topic actual design of vertical flow waterwheel turbine is discussed. Uptill now work on designing and manufacturing of metallic water turbine

for various purposes was done. So accordingly various head ranges turbines like high head, medium head, low head, micro head and pico head were designed, manufactured and was used for different applications. Aim of project is to design and to manufacture the turbine which can be efficiently used which having low design and manufacture cost also should be light in weight. By keeping this concept in mind, different parts of turbine are started to design. Initially primary conceptual drawing is completed. Sizes of parts are limited by space availability, and as type of hydro power is initially decided, which fixes range of power generation. After completing these basic things, next step was to it into 3D parts by using any 3D software. For 3D modeling of these parts Pro-e-wildfire software was used. Now for minimizing weight as well as cost advanced additive manufacturing technology was decided to use namely-Rapid prototyping. What is this RP technology and its different techniques it was explained in earlier chapter. By studying FDM RP technique is finalized. All 3D parts model are shown in appendix-I.

In a design rotor and shaft sizes are more important, by theoretical calculations there is a range in power generation by changing the rotor size. So what was those changes we taken three different sizes of rotor-135mm, 175mm, and 225mm. as a case study. So accordingly RP machine enquiry was done, but cost of machine is few lacs which was not affordable. So decided to write a proposal regarding purchasing of machine. As this process may take few months so it was decided to manufacture all these parts from suppliers. Initially to clear idea about quality and the usefulness of the product manufactured by this RP technique. For this purpose approached to "Design-It Pvt Ltd Company" based in pune (supplier of RP machine). According to the need of technique all 3D models of parts are converted into .STP file, which is further used as an input to RP-Fortus 360mc (FDM machine). Important thing of this technique is that raw material used for manufacturing these parts was thermoplastic, which makes parts light in weight, also life period is more than metallic part as they are free from corrosion, which increases the life of parts. The peoples given estimation of manufacturing cost of those parts which is nearly 1.5lacs. Initially by including all cost parameters manufacturing cost goes very high. But after few years cost of product becomes very less. The parts coming through the machine are end user parts.

Before actually manufacturing these parts it was necessary to analyze the very important part of turbine that is rotor, vanes integrated on outer periphery of rotor. So analysis of vane for checking stress strength at the given condition was checked in ansys14.5 software.

XII.TABULAR PRESENTATION OF ALL ANALYZED PARAMETERS FOR ALL THREE CASES:

Similarly, case three in which rotor size is 225mm and rotor pitch diameter is 250mm also vane size is different having thickness 4mm, height is 50mm.Accordingly results obtained are presented in tabular form as follows:-

Case	Hub dia	PCD	Area	Velocity	force	Pressure	Yield Strength	Von mises stress (Max)	Deformation
	mm	mm	m ²	m/s	N	Pa	Mpa	Pa	m
1	135	150	0.001	1	1	1000	40	904600	0.0001107
			0.001	1.5	2.25	2250	40	2035300	0.00024921
			0.001	2	4	4000	40	3618400	0.00044304
2	175	200	0.0021563	1.5	4.851675	2250	40	1018400	0.00014671
			0.0021563	2	8.6852	4000	40	1810400	0.00026082
			0.0021563	2.5	13.476875	6250	40	2828800	0.00040754
			0.0021563	3	19.4067	9000	40	4073500	0.00058685
3	225	250	0.0026953	1.5	6.064425	2250	40	1009100	0.00014545
			0.0026953	2	10.7812	4000	40	1793900	0.00025858
			0.0026953	2.5	16.845625	6250	40	2803000	0.00040404
			0.0026953	3	24.2577	9000	40	4036300	0.00058182

Table3: Tabular presentation of all analyzed parameters.

XIII. Advantages & Disadvantages of Microturbine- Advantages:

- Especially in mountainous areas where Grid Connection is expensive and unreliable micro hydro turbine is used.
- Micro turbines are few moving parts, compact systems, good efficiency.
- Micro turbines can operate continuously or On-demand and be either grid connected or stand alone. Not like the big hydro plants that use dams and create giant lakes behind the dams, micro-hydro plants only divert a small fraction of the stream and they don't need a water storage pool.
- In rare cases where the site is close to grid lines, part of the produced power can be sold back to the utility, and the grid serves as backup.
- The micro hydro plant requires low maintenance.
- Microhydro systems produce no pollution

DISADVANTAGES:

- As the power demand increases the size of the plant cannot be easily expandable.
- During the summer season there will be less flow and therefore less power output. Advanced planning and research will be needed to ensure adequate energy requirements.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT:

I am very thankful to Prof. P. S. Pingle who was my project guide, he helped me in all ways from starting to the submission of work, also thankful to Mechanical Engineering Department peoples for time to time help. Also thanks to my colleagues who helped me in all ways.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Mohammad Durali, MIT Cambridge, "Design of small water turbine for farms & small communities", 1976.
- 2) O. D. Thapar, Small / Mini hydro power technology, research & Education (state of art), Alternate hydro energy center W.R.D.T.C University of Roorkee,(Unesco regional meeting, Colombo) May-1983
- 3) Alastair Gill, ESD, Neston Paul Mosley, Department of Economics and David J. Fulford, Energy Group, Department of Engineering, "Community Micro Hydro in LDCs: Adoption, Management and Poverty Impact" , July-1999.
- 4) J. L. Gordon, P Engg, "Turbine selection for small low head hydro developments" July 2003.
- 5) Phommachanh, Junichi Nakajima, Chikashi Nakijama, "Development of positive micro hydro turbine" 2006
- 6) Miyoshi Nakijima, Shishnu University, "Performance of savonius turbine for environmentally friendly hydraulic turbine", Dec-2007.
- 7) Abhijit Date, RMIT University, "Low head simple reaction water turbine", April-2009.
- 8) Toshiaki Ikedo, Jio, Kenji Tassuno, Shisnu University, "Performance of nano hydraulic turbine utilizing water" , July-2009
- 9) Fred Collares Pereira Hernandez, Nicholas Mohammed, "Design of a Micro-Hydro Turbine Test Rig", 2009.
- 10) Interim report prepared by Applegate Group, Inc, "Exploring the viability of the low head hydro in colorado's existing irrigation infrastructure" ,Sep'2010.
- 11) Canyon hydro, "Guide to hydropower-an introduction to hydropower concept & planning"
- 12) Dr. R.P. Sani, IIT Roorkee, "Small hydropower generations", May-2011.

- 13) Research article-by-Kailash Golecha, Eldho, & S. V. Prabhu, "Study on the interaction between two hydrokinetic savonius turbines", Nov-2011.
- 14) Ali Arslan, LizwanKhalid, Nassan & Manarvi, Hitech University, taxila, "Design & manufacture of micro zero head turbine for power generation"
- 15) Abhijit Date, AliakbarAkbarzadeh, RMIT university, "Design analysis and the investigation of low head simple reaction water turbine"
- 16) Bryan Patrick-Ho-Yan, "Design of the low head pico hydro turbine for rural electrification in cameroon", April-2012.
- 17) Bilal Abdullah, "Design of high efficiency cross flow turbine for hydro power plant", Feb-2013.
- 18) Sudhir Manoj T. Kshirsagar, Y.S. Rana, KBL pune, "Kirlor brothers in small hydro"
- 19) Bilal Abdullah Nasir, IJEA "Design of micro hydroelectric power station", June-2013.
- 20) Cha-8, "Micro hydro energy resource". FatmaAyaz, UmurAradag, EceOzkaya, "Micro hydro turbine runner design & manufacturing".
- 22) Lokesh Gudukeya, Ignatio Madanhir, "Efficiency improvement of pelton wheel and crossflow turbines in micro hydro power plants: casestudy"
- 23) Abhijit Date and Prof. AliakbarAkbarzadeh, RMIT university, "Design Analysis and Investigation of a Low-Head Simple Reaction Water Turbine".
- 24) "Article on microhydro power"
- 25) Appleyard, D. Opening the Door to India's Small Hydro (2013, January 7).Hydro Capacity., from HydroWorld: <http://www.hydroworld.com>.
- 26) Timo Flaspöhler, "Design of the runner of a Kaplan turbine for small hydroelectric power plants".
- 27) Fred Merryfield (Prof.civil engg), "The banki water turbine".
- 28) Sebastian Hermann, "Design of a micro hydro powered battery charging system for rural village electrification".
- 29) Dilip Singh, Micro Hydro Power Resource Assessment Handbook Prepared for APCTT (Asian and Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology Of the United Nations – Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP), September 2009.
- 30) R.S. Patel, G. I. Joshi,G. H. Joshi, Assessment of Hydropower Potential Through Canal Falls Situated Along Vadodara Branch Canal, May 2014.

WEBSITES:

- 1) NHPC: www.nhpcindia.com
- 2) Ministry of Power: www.powermin.nic.in
- 3) Minihydropowerplants-source- www.google.com

BOOK:

1) Fluid mechanics and hydraulic machines By- R. S. Khurmi.

2) Design of machine elements. By V. B. Bhandari

IJRPET